

NATURE OF AUSTRALIA

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In Australia, getting back to nature is easy. Just head an hour or two out of any city and you can immerse yourself in an unforgettable wilderness experience. It's not just our famous beaches, bush, and outback, either – you can also explore monsoonal wetlands, cool-climate forests and even alpine mountain ranges. These diverse landscapes are home to an amazing range of unique animals and plants.

One of Australia's most distinctive landscapes, "the bush" – native Australian forest – is dominated by tall eucalypts or gum trees, as well as flowering plants like wattles, banksias and waratahs. Right across the country, the bush is a sanctuary for animals such as koalas, wombats and echidnas, and birds such as kookaburras and cockatoos. Plants such as eucalypts have adapted to the bushfires that sometimes sweep through – in fact, many species require fire to stimulate new growth. The Blue Mountains is a one-million-hectare (3,861-square-mile) wilderness with 140 kilometres (87 miles) of hiking trails. Other highlights include Aboriginal cultural sites, cascading waterfalls and the limestone formations and underground rivers of Jenolan Caves. Also well-known for its hiking trails and Aboriginal rock art is the Grampians, in Victoria. It's also home to fantastic wineries, some in operation since the mid-1800s. The highest point on the Australian mainland is Mount Kosciuszko at 2228 metres (7310 feet) above sea level. The glacial lakes and alpine ecosystems of the Australian Alps are unique on this arid continent. In the Southern Forests you'll find some of the world's tallest trees. Karri, jarrah, marri and tingle trees – found nowhere else on Earth – soar up to 70 metres (230 feet) in the sky.

The mainland is the world's smallest continent and the country is the sixth-largest by total area. Australia is sometimes considered the world's largest island and is often dubbed the "island continent". It has 35,877 km (22,293 mi) of coastline (excluding all offshore islands), and claims an exclusive economic zone of 8,148,250 square kilometres (3,146,060 sq mi). This exclusive economic zone does not include the Australian Antarctic Territory.

Australia is one of 17 megadiverse countries. Because of its long geographic isolation, much of Australia's biota is unique. About 94% of its amphibians, 93% of its reptiles and flowering plants, 69% of its mammals and 46% of its birds are endemic. Australia has a wide range of ecosystems of which 89 regions and 419 subregions are recognised in the Australian bioregion framework.

In January 2025 there were 168,386 named species on the Australian National Species List. However, it is estimated that 70% of Australian species have not been discovered and classified and that there may be 600,000 Australian native species. In general, knowledge of vertebrates and flowering plants is better than for invertebrates and fungi. It is estimated that less than 10% of Australia's fungi and insects have been named.

Fitzroy Island, one of the 600 islands within the main archipelago of the Great Barrier Reef

May, 2025-Yil

Most of Australia is arid or semi-arid. In 2021 Australia had 10% of the global permanent meadows and pastureland. Forest cover is around 17% of Australia's land area. The Australian mainland is relatively flat, with an average height of 325 metres (1,066 ft) compared with 870 metres (2,850 ft) for all continents. The Great Dividing Range runs along most of eastern Australia, dividing the central lowlands from the eastern highlands. At 2,228 m (7,310 ft), Mount Kosciuszko is the highest mountain on the mainland. Taller are Mawson Peak, at 2,745 m (9,006 ft), on Heard Island, and, in the Australian Antarctic Territory, Mount McClintock and Mount Menzies, at 3,492 m (11,457 ft) and 3,355 m (11,007 ft) respectively.

The Great Barrier Reef is the world's largest coral reef system and home to amazingly diverse marine life. Above the water, the reef is dotted with picturesque tropical islands and some of the world's most beautiful sun-soaked beaches. You can visit them all on an island escape or from exciting coastal gateways like Cairns and the Whitsundays. Uluru-Kata Tjuta National Park, in the heart of the Red Centre, is home to two of the country's most astounding rock formations – Kata Tjuta and Uluru. The sheer size of these monoliths will impress, as they emerge from an otherwise flat landscape. But it's the spirituality and rich Aboriginal history connected to these sacred places that will leave a lasting impression. Almost too baffling (and beautiful) to believe, Kati Thanda-Lake Eyre in South Australia is known for its beautiful pink hue, stretching across an incredible 144 km (89 mi). Most of the time, the lake is comprised of a dry, sparkling pink salt bed, but once every few years, a downpour of rain floods the region in a dazzling display. The best way to experience the pastel pink spectacle is aboard a scenic flight from the underground opal mining town of Coober Pedy during a half-day adventure with Wrightsair. One of the highlights of the spectacular Great Ocean Road, the 12 Apostles rise defiantly from the wild Southern Ocean, creating spectacular vistas both from above and below. Soar above the remaining spires (there are just eight still standing) in a helicopter, or take the Gibson Steps down to the sand to appreciate the vertical coastal cliffs from another angle.

References

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